

Collective Construction, Negotiation, and Regulation of Gender Meanings Among University Students: A Qualitative Focus Group Study

Valeria Mojica, Laura López, Alejandro Olmos, María Paulina Riveira, Juan Diego Montoya,
Socorro Moreno, and Francisco Palencia-Sánchez

Abstract

Introduction: Gender meanings are socially constructed and shape university life across academic, relational, athletic, and institutional settings. However, there is still limited understanding of the collective processes through which these meanings are constructed, negotiated, and regulated in students' everyday interactions. **Objective:** To explore how university students collectively construct, negotiate, and regulate gender meanings across different contexts of social interaction. **Method:** A descriptive qualitative study was conducted using a semi-structured focus group with seven undergraduate members of the student community at a private university in Bogotá, recruited through an open call. The discussion was organized around four vignettes addressing gender expectations, emotional expression, social media, and institutional inclusion policies. The session was audio-recorded, transcribed verbatim, and analyzed through inductive thematic coding. **Results:** Tensions emerged between normative understandings of gender and more critical perspectives; contextual differences in the regulation of gender expression on campus; the persistence of stereotypes in romantic relationships; and ambivalence regarding the role of social media and the implementation of inclusive policies. The findings suggest that gender operates as a relational and situated process rather than as a fixed or exclusively individual category. **Conclusions:** In this group, gender meanings emerged through collective processes of deliberation, agreement, disagreement, and social regulation. This study provides exploratory evidence of how gender norms are reproduced and also challenged within the university context, and it highlights the importance of participatory and pedagogical institutional strategies to promote inclusion.

Keywords: gender; university students; focus group; qualitative research; inclusion; social interactions.

Introduction

Gender refers to the roles, norms, expectations, and opportunities socially attributed to people and to their gender identities (World Health Organization, 2021). It is a historical and relational construct that varies according to cultural, institutional, and political contexts and has effects on social participation, access to opportunities, and well-being. In different social settings, including the university setting, gender norms influence academic trajectories, interpersonal relationships, experiences of inclusion, and forms of emotional expression (Pino & Edmonds, 2024).

The literature has documented that gender inequalities and stereotypes continue to affect social and working life, as well as perceptions of competence, leadership, and vulnerability (Human

Rights Campaign Foundation, 2022; World Economic Forum, 2025). It has also been described that educational environments are not neutral with respect to gender: peer dynamics, expectations about performance, the regulation of embodiment, and institutional responses to diversity can reinforce or challenge preexisting norms (Koivuhovi et al., 2019; UNESCO, 2022; Wang & Yu, 2023). However, a significant part of this evidence has focused on individual differences or binary models of gender, with less attention to the collective processes through which such meanings are negotiated in everyday interaction.

In the relational domain, gender roles shape expectations regarding affective initiative, care, vulnerability, and power within couples (Bode et al., 2025). Similarly, in digital spaces and social networks, processes of validation, exposure, and controversy can amplify both the questioning and the reproduction of stereotypes (Alamri & Alamri, 2026; Alwulahi, 2025). These tensions become especially visible in the university context, where formal and informal interaction settings converge and where institutions implement inclusion policies that may generate adherence, debate, or resistance.

Understanding how gender meanings are constructed and regulated among university students is relevant because it makes it possible to identify not only individual effects but also collective mechanisms of validation, sanction, negotiation, and change (Koudenburg et al., 2021). Accordingly, this study sought to explore how university students collectively construct, negotiate, and regulate gender meanings in different contexts of social interaction, based on the group discussion of thematic vignettes.

Method

A descriptive qualitative study was conducted with a semi-structured focus group. Prior to the study, the team carried out a literature search in academic databases to contextualize the problem and support the design of the discussion vignettes. The initial sample consisted of seven undergraduate students from a private university in Bogotá, recruited through an open invitation. The inclusion criteria were: being an active undergraduate student, being of legal age, and voluntarily agreeing to participate through informed consent. Graduate students were excluded.

Procedure

The session was structured around four vignettes addressing gender expectations among peers, emotional expression in romantic relationships, gender regulation on social media, and institutional inclusion policies. At the beginning, the activity dynamics were explained and participants were informed about the audio recording. To preserve confidentiality, each participant was assigned a numerical identifier. The discussion was guided by semi-structured orienting questions. During the session, four of the seven participants withdrew starting with the third vignette; therefore, the last two vignettes were discussed by a smaller number of participants, an aspect that was considered in the interpretation of the findings. The recording lasted approximately 50 minutes and was transcribed verbatim for subsequent analysis.

Data Analysis

An exhaustive reading of the transcript was conducted, followed by inductive thematic coding aimed at identifying emerging categories, argumentative tensions, points of agreement and disagreement, and forms of discursive regulation of gender. Subsequently, the codes were grouped into semantic categories organized according to each vignette. Given the exploratory nature of the study and the small group size, the results should be interpreted as situated findings and not as generalizable statements about the entire university population.

Ethical considerations: Participation was voluntary, and informed consent was obtained before the start of the session. Basic confidentiality measures were implemented, including the use of numerical identifiers in the transcript and in the presentation of excerpts from participants' contributions.

Results

The analysis was organized around four vignettes designed to explore gender expectations among peers, emotional expression in romantic relationships, gender regulation on social media, and institutional inclusion policies. Based on the verbatim transcript, emerging thematic categories and patterns of group interaction were identified. Overall, the discussion showed that the meaning of gender was collectively constructed through partial agreements, argumentative controversies, and successive reformulations among participants.

Vignette 2 concentrated the greatest volume of deliberation and disagreement, especially around the relative weight of sociocultural and biological factors. Vignette 3 prompted longer and more reflective interventions, with less interpersonal confrontation. Vignette 1 generated broader agreement regarding the existence of gender pressures and their psychosocial effects. Vignette 4, discussed by a smaller group because of participant withdrawal during the session, focused on the practical feasibility and tensions associated with implementing institutional inclusion measures.

Vignette 1: Gender Expectations Among Peers

In this vignette, a normative conception clearly emerged that associates masculinity with strength, emotional control, and endurance, and femininity with vulnerability or sensitivity. Participants described these expectations as socially rooted rules that are often presented as natural, although several of them also explicitly questioned them.

Participants noted that gender regulation does not operate homogeneously within the university but varies across academic and social contexts. Spaces perceived as relatively more open were contrasted with others considered more normative. The excerpts discussed included experiences of pressure to conform to assigned gender and institutional or interpersonal difficulties in recognizing nonbinary identities, including the inappropriate use of pronouns. These

contributions suggest that, for this group, the university constitutes a heterogeneous space in which openness, lack of knowledge, and everyday regulatory practices coexist.

Pressure on masculinity was exemplified particularly in sports contexts. There, expressing pain, fatigue, or discomfort was described as a sign of weakness or lack of commitment, showing how certain environments can reinforce models of physical toughness and emotional restraint. This finding suggests that gender regulation takes situated forms and that some settings more strongly intensify the performance mandates associated with masculinity.

Vignette 2: Emotional Expression and Stereotypes in Romantic Relationships

The second vignette was organized around three main axes: the discussion between sociocultural and biological explanations of gender, stereotypes about emotional expression, and gender roles in romantic relationships. Some participants appealed to hormonal, neuroscientific, or evolutionary arguments to explain differences between men and women, while others insisted that the way emotions are felt and expressed depends largely on historical and cultural processes. Rather than being resolved, this tension showed the coexistence of different interpretive frameworks within the group.

Regarding emotional expression, participants pointed out that differential expectations persist regarding which emotions are socially acceptable for each gender. It was mentioned that, in many contexts, men are still expected to repress sadness or vulnerability, while affective initiative or the open expression of female desire continues to be evaluated through normative frameworks. Although some participants perceived generational changes and greater openness in certain environments, they also considered that these stereotypes continue to have force in everyday life.

With respect to romantic relationships, traditional schemes were described in which the man appears as provider and the woman as caregiver or primary source of emotional support. Strikingly, some participants suggested that even in same-sex couples, classifications between the “masculine” and the “feminine” may be reproduced. This finding should not be interpreted as a universal rule, but rather as an indication of the persistence of cultural gender frameworks that may also organize relational expectations in non-heterosexual relationships.

Vignette 3: Public Spaces, Social Media, and Gender Regulation

The third vignette focused on the role of public spaces and social media in gender regulation. Participants described digital platforms as amplifiers of social reactions to gender expressions that challenge traditional stereotypes. The discussion included the idea that algorithms may reinforce prior opinions and contribute to polarization, while also favoring the accelerated circulation of content and positions.

It was also proposed that the digital environment facilitates the expression of opinions that might not be voiced in the same way in face-to-face interactions, partly because of relative anonymity

and the absence of direct contact. For some participants, this feature expands possibilities for expression and identification; for others, it may also intensify dynamics of aggression, social pressure, or uncritical validation.

Overall, this vignette suggests that social media were understood simultaneously as spaces of recognition, discourse circulation, and identity construction, but also as settings of regulation, controversy, and exposure. The discussion showed an ambivalent assessment of their role in contemporary processes of gender signification.

Vignette 4: Inclusion Policies and Institutional Tensions

The fourth vignette focused on institutional inclusion policies and the tensions associated with their implementation. Participants recognized that this type of measure can represent progress in the recognition of diverse identities; however, they also expressed reservations about the way such policies are introduced when they are not accompanied by pedagogical strategies, sufficient information, or spaces for community participation.

One of the issues that generated the greatest controversy was gender-neutral restrooms. The conversation included concerns related to recognition, comfort, modesty, and hygiene, which shows that student responses to inclusive measures are not homogeneous. Rather than a univocal rejection or linear acceptance, the discussion revealed tensions between principles of inclusion, perceptions of practical feasibility, and the need for collective deliberation.

In general terms, participants agreed that inclusive policies would have greater legitimacy if they were constructed through gradual, pedagogical, and participatory processes. This result suggests that, in the context analyzed, institutional inclusion was understood not only as a normative problem but also as a process of social translation that requires dialogue, awareness-raising, and negotiation among different actors in the university community.

Discussion

The findings of this study suggest that gender, in the university context examined, does not operate solely as an individual identity but as a relational process that is configured and regulated in interaction. Through the focus group, it was possible to observe how participants draw on different cultural repertoires—normative, critical, biologist, experiential, and institutional—to explain, justify, or question gender expectations in everyday settings. In this sense, the study contributes a process-oriented perspective on the construction of gender meaning among university students.

Consistent with previous literature, the results indicate that different university contexts shape the degree of openness or sanction toward non-normative gender expressions. The discussion about faculties, peer dynamics, and sports spaces showed that gender regulation is situated: some environments appear to favor greater reflexivity, while others more intensely reinforce ideals of toughness, self-control, or conformity to assigned gender. This finding is consistent with the idea

that gender norms are not distributed homogeneously but take specific forms depending on the interaction setting (Koivuhovi et al., 2019; Shiakou et al., 2026).

At the relational level, the persistence of differentiated expectations regarding rationality, vulnerability, provision, and care suggests that gender stereotypes continue to organize the interpretation of romantic relationships (Bode et al., 2025). The fact that some participants described the reproduction of “masculine” and “feminine” schemes even in same-sex couples may be read, in an exploratory way, as an indication of the cultural strength of these frameworks. Nevertheless, given the qualitative design and situated nature of the study, this observation should be understood as an analytical clue rather than as a generalization about all non-heterosexual relationships.

A particularly relevant point was the coexistence of biological and sociocultural explanations of gender within the same conversation. Rather than being resolved in favor of one position or the other, the debate showed that participants mobilize heterogeneous interpretive frameworks to make sense of differences, tensions, and personal experiences. From an analytical perspective, this coexistence invites us to avoid both biologicist reductionism and overly simplifying formulations of social constructivism, and it underscores the need to analyze how these repertoires are articulated in everyday conversation (Wang & Yu, 2023).

The ambivalent assessment of social media also deserves attention. For participants, these platforms function both as spaces of recognition and identification and as settings that intensify controversies, validate biases, and facilitate forms of social regulation at high speed. This result is consistent with contemporary debates on the role of digital environments in the circulation of social norms and in the amplification of gender-related tensions (Alamri & Alamri, 2026; Alwulaii, 2025).

Finally, the discussion on inclusive policies suggests that, for this group, acceptance of institutional measures depends not only on their normative content but also on the conditions of implementation. The insistence on gradual, pedagogical, and participatory processes can be interpreted as a demand for social legitimacy around institutional changes. In practical terms, this indicates that university inclusion strategies could be strengthened when they incorporate deliberation, clear information, and listening spaces that allow tensions to be processed without reducing them to binary positions of support or rejection (Aldossari & Murphy, 2024; UNESCO, 2022; Worthington et al., 2020).

Taken together, the study suggests that gender meanings among university students are produced within a web of experiences, contexts, and collective negotiations. The main contribution of the manuscript is to show that gender norms are not only internalized but also discussed, disputed, and reformulated in interaction. At the same time, the results should be read in light of their exploratory scope and the limitations derived from the sample size, the composition of the group, and the reduction in the number of participants in the last vignettes.

This study has several limitations. First, it was based on a single focus group with a small number of participants, which restricts the transferability of the findings. Second, the withdrawal of four participants starting with the third vignette reduced the breadth of perspectives in the final part of the discussion. Third, the open call may have favored the participation of students with greater willingness or prior interest in the topic. Finally, because this was an exploratory qualitative study conducted in a specific institutional context, the results should be interpreted as situated and not generalizable.

Conclusions

The results suggest that gender meanings among university students are not configured in a fixed or exclusively individual manner, but emerge from collective processes of interaction, negotiation, and social regulation. In this group, gender appeared as a situated category, shaped by cultural norms, personal experiences, argumentative controversies, and the specific conditions of each interaction context. The study provides exploratory evidence on the ways in which these norms are reproduced, questioned, and, in some cases, transformed within the university environment.

These findings support the importance of promoting university spaces that not only formulate inclusion policies but also facilitate pedagogical and deliberative processes for their social appropriation. Future studies could expand participant diversity, compare faculties or institutional contexts, and incorporate multiple focus groups or in-depth interviews to explore the variability of these experiences in greater detail.

Conflict of Interest

The authors declare that they have no conflicts of interest related to this study. The work was developed within the framework of the well-being in education policy with the aim of strengthening it.

References

- Aldossari, M., & Murphy, S. E. (2024). Inclusion is in the eye of the beholder: A relational analysis of the role of gendered moral rationalities in Saudi Arabia. *Work, Employment and Society*, 38(5), 1244-1266. <https://doi.org/10.1177/09500170231180823>
- Alamri, A., & Alamri, I. (2026). Stereotypes, gender norms, and victim blaming: Attributions of responsibility for stranger harassment. *Acta Psychologica*, 262, Article 106189. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.actpsy.2025.106189>
- Alwulaii, A. N. (2025). Body, gender, race and fatness in social studies: Gap and future. *Frontiers in Sociology*, 10, Article 1525944. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fsoc.2025.1525944>

- Bode, A., Luoto, S., & Kavanagh, P. S. (2025). Sex differences in romantic love: An evolutionary perspective. *Biology of Sex Differences*, 16(1), Article 16. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s13293-025-00698-4>
- Human Rights Campaign Foundation. (2022). The LGBTQ+ women's wage gap in the United States. Human Rights Campaign Foundation.
- Koudenburg, N., Kannegieter, A., Postmes, T., & Kashima, Y. (2021). The subtle spreading of sexist norms. *Group Processes & Intergroup Relations*, 24(8), 1467-1485. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1368430220961838>
- Koivuhovi, S., Vainikainen, M.-P., Kalalahti, M., & Niemivirta, M. (2019). Changes in children's agency beliefs and control expectancy in classes with and without a special emphasis in Finland from grade four to grade six. *Scandinavian Journal of Educational Research*, 63(3), 427-442. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00313831.2017.1402364>
- Pino, M., & Edmonds, D. M. (2024). Misgendering, cisgenderism and the reproduction of the gender order in social interaction. *Sociology*, 58(6), 1243-1262. <https://doi.org/10.1177/00380385241237194>
- Shiakou, M., Alexopoulos, A., Vasou, C., Nicolaou, P., Epaminonda, M., & Neofitides, S. (2026). Adolescent football players' attitudes in Cyprus toward gender stereotypes, masculinity, and gender-based violence. *Violence Against Women*, 32(1), 133-157. <https://doi.org/10.1177/10778012241309361>
- UNESCO. (2022). Equity, inclusion and pluralism in higher education. UNESCO.
- Wang, L., & Yu, Z. (2023). Gender-moderated effects of academic self-concept on achievement, motivation, performance, and self-efficacy: A systematic review. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 14, Article 1136141. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2023.1136141>
- Worthington, R. L., Stanley, C. A., & Smith, D. G. (2020). Advancing the professionalization of diversity officers in higher education: Report of the Presidential Task Force on the Revision of the NADOHE standards of professional practice. *Journal of Diversity in Higher Education*, 13(1), 1-22. <https://doi.org/10.1037/dhe0000175>
- World Health Organization. (2021, May 24). Gender and health. World Health Organization. <https://www.who.int/news-room/questions-and-answers/item/gender-and-health>
- World Economic Forum. (2025). Global gender gap report 2025. World Economic Forum.